

To inscribe figures on the ground: Alice's Adventures in Borgesland

Flatbeds-landscape urbanism
Final paper (August 23 99)

Roger Paez i Blanch
Prof. James Corner

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Intro

JABBERWOCKY

*'Twas brillig, and the slithy toves
Did gyre and gimble in the wabe:
All mimsy were the borogoves,
And the mome raths outgrabe.*
Lewis Carroll¹

"--the table upon which, since the beginning of time, language has intersected space."
Michel Foucault²

"-- En su laberinto sobran tres líneas - dijo por fin -. Yo se de un laberinto griego que es una línea unica, recta. En esa línea se han perdido tantos filosofos que bien puede perderse un mero detective."
Jorge Luis Borges³

The present essay stems from the re-placing of an observation within the framework built up during the course's duration⁴.

-The observation is that of the ground as a fundamental construction, one that turns a fragment of the earth's surface into an inscribe-able ground: ground bearer of signs; ground where geometry is made possible; ground shaped by climate, action, and language alike.

-The framework is provided by the series of nine flatbeds papers annexed, that are to be read as an instruction manual⁵.

-The site for the game, the linking device in the sense of Foucault's *tabula*⁶, is Alice's performance in "Through the Looking-glass".

¹ Cf. Carroll, Lewis, "Through the Looking-glass and what Alice found there", in "The Annotated Alice", Introduction and Notes by Martin Gardiner, Charles N. Potter, Inc. Publisher, New York 1960, page 191.

² Cf. Foucault, Michel, "The Order of Things", Preface, page xvii.

³ Cf. Borges, Jorge Luis, "La Muerte y la Brujula", in "Ficciones", in "Obra Completa", Emece Editores, Barcelona-Buenos Aires. English translation: "Death and the Compass", in "Fictions".

⁴ "Flatbeds: landscape urbanism", Professor James Corner, AAD programme, GSAPP, Columbia University, Summer 1999.

⁵ Please refer to annex 1: "Flatbeds-landscape urbanism: nine papers".

⁶ "But all these worms and snakes, all these creatures redolent of decay and slime are slithering, like the syllables which designate them, in Eusthene's saliva: that is where they all have their *common locus*, like the umbrella and the sewing-machine on the operating table."

In its own way, this paper attempts a flatbed operation, i.e. dealing with many agents, it tries to construct a coherent game without reducing all the players to an overarching ideology of the game proper. What is being tested here, is the possibility of building up a contention using live material –be it constructions, images, debates, situations, or statements. To put it in other words, trying to set up a game board for players not reducible to it, although *consistent* with it.

This experiment does not see itself as a mere academic exercise, but it touches upon pressing topics in the practice of architecture nowadays⁷, and it hints at new modes of contemporary practice to match the time's challenges⁸.

Aiming at a definitive deconstruction of dual thought⁹, the present essay resists being understood in terms of content as opposed to form. Style¹⁰ is understood as meaningful: there is no clear-cut distinction between what is being said and how it is being said. A bird cannot but communicate through its actual performance¹¹ as much as the White King (and/or his pencil) says, through Jabberwocky, everything he has to say precisely the way it has to be said¹². By the same token that confronting Jabberwocky in terms of strict sense (or nonsense, for that matter) is clearly insufficient, confronting this essay only in terms of content does not capture its intended performance.

The will to make impossible the segregation of the presented material at play and the contention being made mirrors the criticism to the split between theory

"I use the word "table" in two superimposed senses: the nickel-plate, rubbery table swatched in white, glittering beneath a glass sun devouring all shadow –the table where, for an instant, perhaps forever, the umbrella encounters the sewing-machine; and also a table, a *tabula*, that enables thought to operate upon the entities of our world, to put them in order, to divide them according to classes, to group them according to names that designate their similarities and their differences –the table upon which, since the beginning of time, language has intersected space." Foucault, Michel, op. cit. pages xvi-xvii.

⁷ When we refer to "architecture", unless otherwise indicated, we are understanding the field of practices around what is conventionally known as architecture, urbanism, landscape architecture and urban design. We keep the old name "architecture" for its etymology (arkhi-techne: primeval-adaptation) allows for a much higher degree of redefinition within the same compact labeling.

⁸ To match the time's challenge in the sense of (fully) engaging the novel modes of comprehension and management of reality: "To ride the *Zeitgeist* as the surfer rides the waves" (Rem Koolhaas). We are not inferring any Truth from the *Zeitgeist*, we are merely acknowledging its force. We are not interested in the *Zeitgeist* as a moral legitimization, but in using its inertia – redirecting it.

Please refer to annex 2: "Provisional hints for a contemporary criticality. Tafuri vs Koolhaas".

⁹ Dual thought is embodied in architectural practice in the form of oppositions such as theory/practice or artist/engineer. Moreover, duality is also expressed in the uneasy relationship if not obvious suspicion respect the issue of money. Current architectural practice still gathers the fruits of a long history of artistic practices' distrust with regards to (earning) money. A fundamental issue of morality is raised here. For the essay's statement, it is sufficient to point it out, although a detailed discussion of the matter would surely prove to be fertile in extreme for a re-situating of architectural practices within the landscape of current labour-force organization.

¹⁰ We understand style along the lines of Deleuze's account of bird songs. Cf Deleuze, Gilles, "A Thousand Plateaus. Capitalism and Schizophrenia", University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis.

¹¹ It is not that the bird communicates a *something* through a *somehow*, but rather the something pertains to the somehow itself.

¹² Cf. Carroll, Lewis, op. cit. , pp 190-191.

and practice still so very current in society at large. Like Alice, we will be playing with live creatures that perform the non-marginal resistance De Certeau refers to: “these multiform, tricky, resistance and stubborn procedures that elude discipline without being outside the field in which it is exercised”¹³. Like Alice, these creatures do frame our game but they do not overdetermine it. The flatbed provides the framework that enables such operation¹⁴.

Sector one

ALICE AND THE CHESSBOARD

“I declare it’s marked out just like a chess-board ! (...) It’s a great huge game of chess that’s being played –all over the world–“
Lewis Carroll¹⁵

Right in the beginning of the infamous second helping of Alice’s adventures, Lewis Carroll sets the narrative the reader is about to enter in the form of a chess problem. Besides the intrinsic interest of accounting for the same story through means so different as writing and chess, Rev. C. L. Dodgson’s move has many other implications. Through his image, Carroll draws a connection between the world (more accurately, the ground) and a chessboard. Moreover, the characters inhabiting the world behind the mirror, consciously or not (that point is never quite disclosed) participate in a huge game that will eventually lead to the coronation of Queen Alice. Their actions are readable, from a cosmic gaze¹⁶, as having a sense (if not a meaning) other than that recognizable from the surface. According to Martin Gardiner, Carroll stages here the first attempt to “base a fictional narrative on animated chess pieces”¹⁷, although surely the association of the land with a chessboard is a much older one¹⁸. The cross-referencing of the

¹³ Please refer to annex 2 : “Provisional hints for a contemporary criticality. Tafuri vs Koolhaas”, for a detailed discussion on the issue of non-marginality and criticality.

¹⁴ For a more detailed discussion on the concept of flatbed and its framework affiliations, please refer to “Flatbeds-landscape urbanism. Paper eight- FLATBEDS”, in annex 1.

¹⁵ Cf. Carroll, Lewis, op. cit. pp 207-208.

¹⁶ Not dissimilar to the gaze from the top of the World Trade Centre in Manhattan as accounted for Michel De Certeau. Cf. De Certeau, Michel, “Walking the City” in “The Practice of Everyday Life”, Translated by Steven Rendall, University of California Press. Further on we insist in the issue of the gaze, refer to “Borges, Chesterton, Auster”.

¹⁷ Cf. Carroll, Lewis, op. cit. page 172.

¹⁸ Cf. Rabelais, “Gargantua and Pantagruel”, Book 5, Chapters 24 and 25.

Particularly interesting is Wells story, inspired in the Book of Job, where God and the devil are playing chess:

“But the chess they play is not the little ingenious game that originated in India; it is on an altogether different scale. The Ruler of the Universe creates the board, the pieces, and the rules; he makes all the moves; (...) his antagonist, however, is permitted to introduce a slight inexplicable inaccuracy into each move, which necessitates further moves in correction. (...) Apparently, the adversary cannot win, but also he cannot lose so long as he can keep the game going. But he is concerned, it would seem, in preventing the development of any reasoned scheme in the game.”, Wells, H.G., “The Undying Fire”.

chess game with the story, not only provides the latter with a regulatory structure, but most importantly it displaces the narrative from a particular kind of horizon (a linguistic one), operating a proliferation not only of the events but also of their meaning¹⁹.

BORGES, CHESTERTON, AUSTER

Borges, Jorge Luis: Death and the Compass.

Lonnrot the detective is faced with a case of murder. When a second murder comes along, he discovers the thread linking the two, and infers the time and place where a third murder will be committed. The link that ties them together becomes obvious once the ground is recognized as a huge blackboard where the murderer draws, through the action of killing, a perfect triangle, both in space and time. Attempting to prevent the third murder, Lonnrot discovers, too late, that the whole labyrinth traced upon the ground by Red Scharlach the criminal, is nothing more than a trap to kill him, the third and final murder.

*Chesterton, Gilbert Keith: The Death of Major Brown, in The Club of Queer Trades.*²⁰

Major Brown, a rich and retired military man and amateur horticulturist, strolls around London when he finds a working man carrying a wheelbarrow full of an extremely rare kind of yellow flowers, the Major's favourite ones. The Major gets a real shock, as he was trying to get hold of that very species for a long time through the most prestigious and knowable botanical institutions without any success: these are too rare a breed. Overcoming his initial disgust to working men, Major Brown finally asks him where did he get the flowers. The answer is also unexpected: I just picked 'em from the backyard o'er there. Go get some yerself, there are plenty. Breaking all the codes a respectable man like him should observe, Major Brown peeps from the top of the garden wall to see a neat lawn with a huge yellow flowerbed right in its centre. The flowerbed, viewed from above, reads: DEATH TO MAJOR BROWN.

The reputed chess skills of Death are thus not surprising. Refer to Ingmar Bergman's "The Seventh Seal" *leit motif*, framing the whole film: the Death and the knight playing a game of chess of grave affiliations, not reduced to the game itself.

¹⁹ A chess problem as posed for Carroll has more than a single determinate solution. Donald M. Liddell, in the "British Chess Magazine" of May 1910 (Vol. 30, page 181), attempted to work out a better sequence of chess moves that would both fit the narrative and at the same time conform to all the rules of the game. One could conversely try to work out virtual narratives that would fit the multiple solutions of the chess problem as presented, enacting a true proliferation of Alice's adventures through the Looking-glass. What Mr Liddell set aside, in an over-zealous approach to the chess game's regulatory role, was precisely the horizon opened up by the game itself, once the inter-relationship of game and story has been accepted. Chess acts here like a true cosmogony, i.e. rather than offering necessary solutions, it sets up the framework in relation to which actions will be situated.

²⁰ Cf. Chesterton, Gilbert Keith, "The Death of Major Brown", in "The Club of Queer Trades", Penguin, London.

*Auster, Paul: City of Glass, in The New York Trilogy.*²¹

Quinn, a writer hired as a detective, has been following Stillman for days. Stillman's meanderings around the Upper West Side did not seem to make any sense whatsoever: the old man walked all day, very slowly, not venturing outside a particular area of the city, picking up little bits of rubbish and scribbling in his red notebook. When Quinn was about to give up trying to make any sense of Stillman's action, he traced on top of the city map, the movements Stillman had made on a single day. He repeated the procedure for two more days, until he had no doubt about it: Stillman had been writing with his steps, one letter a day, a message: THE TOWER OF BABEL.

"Lonrot evito los ojos de Scharlach. Miro a los arboles y el cielo subdivididos en rombos turbiamente amarillos, verdes y rojos. Sintio un poco de frio y una tristeza impersonal, casi anonima. Ya era de noche; desde el polvoriento jardin subio el grito inutil de un pajaro. Lonrot considero por ultima vez el problema de las muertes simetricas y periodicas.

-- En su laberinto sobran tres líneas - dijo por fin -. Yo se de un laberinto griego que es una línea unica, recta. En esa línea se han perdido tantos filosofos que bien puede perderse un mero detective.

Scharlach, cuando en otro avatar usted me de caza, finja (o cometa) un crimen en A, luego un segundo crimen en B, a 8 kilometros de A, luego un tercer crimen en C, a 4 kilometros de A y de B, a mitad de camino entre los dos. Aguardeme despues en D, a dos kilometros de A y de C, de nuevo a mitad de camino. Mateme en D, como ahora va a matarme en Triste-Le-Roy.

-- Para la otra vez que lo mate -- replico Scharlach ---le prometo ese laberinto, que consta de una sola línea recta y que es invisible; incesante.

Retrocedio unos pasos. Despues, muy cuidadosamente, hizo fuego."

Jorge Luis Borges²²

The last lines of Borges' short story "Death and the Compass" resonate in a fair amount of posterior and even previous literature. In his own idiosyncratic way, Borges distills far-reaching insights into apparently tame and pristine sentences. The story's underlying motive is that of the readable quality of constructed ground (the city being, of course, its utmost example). The ground, as opposed to the un-ritualized earth surface, is one that has been constructed, be it through actual physical action that transforms its appearance (phenomenological

²¹ Cf. Auster, Paul, "City of Glass", in "The New York Trilogy", volume I, Sun & Moon Press, Los Angeles, 1985. Refer especially to pages 104 to 113.

²² Id. Footnote 3.

transformation), be it by ritual²³ alone that transforms its being (ontological transformation).

The ground's main quality is its ability to receive meaning. The simile of the ground with a game-board or a traceable plane comes to show that in such a setting, action is meaningful. In its previous stage²⁴, the unruléd crust of the earth, albeit essentially emergent, could not frame meaning. As Leatherbarrow puts it, relating the story told by Pherecydes of Syros, according to which the world was formed when Zeus threw a matrimonial veil over the head of the goddess of the underworld:

“the lines and light from the sky *articulated* the ground; Zeus-work served the soil by providing a framework for its voice. Veiled or praised in this way, Chthonia, who had been darkly parthenogenetic, (...) became Gaia, still abundant after the veil, but no longer emergent (*parthenos*) –rather, emerged and, consequently, visible.

The veil, map, or woven cloth was thus a trace of the act by which soil appeared within an articulated framework. Until that time, while still unveiled, unwoven, unlined, dark earth had been (and would have remained) uncharted and unnavigable, like the sea, expanding and absorbing. By means of this chart of horizontals [the woven veil] the earth was shown to be a livable horizon, matter having been abbreviated into a mat.”²⁵

A reminder of Zeus' fundamental cosmogenic act is staged in every (conscious or unconscious) ritualizing of the land, by virtue of which soil becomes ground, bearer of meaning inscribed through action^{26,27}. Such ritualizings vary from the

²³ Many pages have been written on that subject. Joseph Rykwert (drawing heavily on Fustel de Coulanges) has called attention upon the essentially ritual character of city foundation –i.e. the need to construct a transcendent framework to allow for inhabitation. Inhabitation (and mostly sedentary inhabitation) is only possible in the double play of (1) begging for forgiveness (to the Earth or the Gods) for the fundamental crime of wounding the E-earth, and (2) actualize the violence infringed in the very act of inhabitation: to penetrate the E-earth's surface in order to dwell on it. Both the rituals (foundation spikes, for instance) and the physical configurations of the safe havens of/inhabitation (walls and gates, for instance), belong to the above mentioned double play, by virtue of which the act of inhabitation is revealed as an act of utter (if necessary) violence (to the E-earth). Particularly interesting in the present framework is Margueron's account of Mesopotamian city foundations. Cf. Margueron, Jean-Claude, “Mesopotamia”, Ediciones Catedra, Barcelona 1996.

²⁴ Previous in a logical sense, not chronological, for we are not dealing here with a time continuum. Previous should not be understood in the patronizing sense often mobilized from the modern time of progress.

²⁵ Cf. Leatherbarrow, David, “Leveling the land”, in “Recovering Landscape”, James Corner, ed., Princeton Architectural Press, 1999. page 175.

²⁶ An interesting issue is raised here: should architecture inscribe meaning in the world through action, or should it simply create ground, i.e. construct (a) framework for meaning to be inscribed? Such question resonates in manifold contemporary texts, cf. for instance Allen, Stan, “Infrastructural Urbanism”, in “Points+Lines”, Princeton Architectural Press, 1999.

We leave the question of “what meaning” to the philosophers, although quite clearly we are not referring to any sort of capital M meaning, but rather to a sense, in the same way an arrow has a sense.

haruspex's techniques to found a city²⁸ to the leveling of the plots in a contemporary suburban development. Borges' short story captures the culturally constructed character of the ground. The very act of writing –through action, be it planting flowerbeds, walking or murdering- in the ground, more than implying any kind of cosmic eye to whom every single move in this planet would be an infinitesimal fragment of a (the) universal text, celebrates the charged character of the ground acknowledged as a constructed horizon.

Borges' story relates to two other literary exercises that very clearly resonate with it, forming a curious trilogy on the issue of "writing on the ground": Borges' admired G.K. Chesterton²⁹, and Borges-admiring Paul Auster³⁰. These three stories enter into extremely interesting relationships, proliferating outside their original frames³¹.

"Quinn's thoughts momentarily flew off to the concluding pages of A. Gordon Pym and to the discovery of the strange hieroglyphs on the inner wall of the chasm—letters inscribed into the earth itself."

Paul Auster [emphasis added]³².

Sector two

LEVEL

The planar nature of the ground, as staged by the above mentioned trilogy, is also a scabby one. To write upon the earth is to wound it, inflicting violence to the crust of the earth –the ground- by engraving in it: *letters inscribed into the earth itself*.

Such gesture³³ is a fundamentally architectonic one. In it, what is ultimately being dealt with (what is ultimately at stake) is the issue of level.

The acknowledgement of the ground as a constructed plane (the chess-board, the draughting-board) is made evident in the city, through the superimposed

²⁷ Not strictly human action is understandable as an engraver. For the issue of the "antropofugical" shift, please refer to annex 2, "Post-humanism and ecological thought", page 3.

²⁸ The haruspex re-replaces the centre of the world in the central spot of the future city engraving, on the ground, the *mundus*, the fundamental cross that at once settles and defines the city. Cf. works by Joseph Rykwert and Fustel de Coulanges on the greco-roman ritual foundations of cities.

²⁹ Cf. Chesterton, Gilbert Keith, "The Death of Major Brown", in "The Club of Queer Trades", Penguin, London.

³⁰ Cf. Auster, Paul, "City of Glass", in "The New York Trilogy", volume I, Sun & Moon Press, Los Angeles, 1985. Refer especially to pages 104 to 113.

³¹ Some of these relationships, it can be claimed, are consciously planned, as Borges was a reader of Chesterton, and Auster a reader of Borges.

³² Cf. Auster, Paul, op. cit. page 111.

³³ We are using gesture along the lines of Flusser. Cf. Flusser, W. : "Los Gestos", Anagrama, Barcelona.

ground floor(s) strata. Such accumulation of grounds, of reference planes, is not limited to historical strata³⁴, and so it raises an awareness of the essentially consistent time of the city, where multiple realities, synchronic or not, coexist in the same plane, allowing for a transchronic mode of operating (within time)³⁵. Negotiating the level is among the most fundamental architectonic acts.

FLAT

We have lately been confronted with a renewed interest in flatness. From Flatland to Mille Plateaux³⁶, a recurring insistence in flatness is noticeable. The course we are about to finish proposed the “flatbed” as a relevant concept for architectural-related practices. Most interestingly, the flatbed is not a clear-cut denomination for a particular framework. Rather, its potential is detonated through the shifts and swerves it undergoes when it affiliates with the different frameworks through which architecture is negotiated, such as representation, methodology, organization, site, or production³⁷. Certain characteristics, nevertheless, recur in all these associations, namely procedure, connectivity, proliferation and collapse³⁸.

Our interest in flatness goes beyond metaphor, flatness, as collapsed distance, involves modes of operation we believe very relevant for contemporary practice in the so-called network society. Flatness is not a given condition, i.e. it involves the action of flattening³⁹. Flatness, thus, works conceptually in a collapsed

³⁴ Many works of architecture quite explicitly confront this issue. An interesting case is that of Sinan's Rustem Pasa Mosque in Istanbul, where the elevation of the mosque's ground to use the ground floor for commercial purposes redefines a new ground floor above the physical one -one that, in its turn, is standing on top of an indefinite number of ancient grounds, some of which actually affiliate with the everyday life, in the form of basements, wells, *hani* courts, underpasses, crypts, tunnels, etc. The new ground constructed twelve feet above “the” ground, in its turn proliferates into a web of connections: a physical image of the city's parallel and incongruent times collapsed into a flat and consistent plane.

Alex Wall's conceptualization of the urban surface as the agent of consistency of the urban condition appears as a relevant one in that framework. Cf. Wall, Alex, “Programming the Urban Surface”, in “Recovering Landscape”, James Corner, editor, Princeton Architectural Press, 1999, page 233 ff.

³⁵ Transchronic implies an *active* relationship with history, and a non-linear temporality that compels one to face the constructed character of (any) history, as well as the non-metaphorical presence of (a number of) pasts.

For a further developing of the concept of transchronicity, please refer to annex 1: “Flatbeds-landscape urbanism, paper six: The Specificity of Site”, and annex 2: “History”.

³⁶ Cf. Abbott, Thomas, “Flatland”, Penguin, London; and Deleuze, Gilles / Guattari, Felix, “Introduction: Rhizome”, in “A Thousand Plateaus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia”, University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis.

³⁷ For a further developing of the flatbed's affiliation with the above frameworks, please refer to our “Flatbeds-paper eight (July 21 99): Flatbeds”.

³⁸ Id.

³⁹ Ultimately, flatness is the framework of multiplicity, as opposed to the subject-object dualism of mainstream western thought. Such is (a) very topic (if one can use such a term) of Deleuze and Guattari's investigations in Mille Plateaux: “There is no unity to serve as a pivot in the object, or to divide in the subject.(...) A multiplicity has neither subject nor object, only determinations,

condition, where depth is flattened onto a plane of consistency. The two main outcomes of such collapse, as Deleuze and Guattari have already shown⁴⁰, are on the one hand proliferational immanency, and an operativity of reorientation on the other⁴¹. Not only the very understanding of the world, but perhaps most importantly the modes of operation within it are radically affected by such conception of flatness: flatness as collapsed depth.

magnitudes, and dimensions that cannot increase in number without the multiplicity changing in nature." "Flat multiplicities of n dimensions are asignifying and asubjective", op. cit. pp 8 and 9.

⁴⁰ Cf. Deleuze and Guattari, op. cit., especially "Principle of multiplicity", pp 8-9.

⁴¹ "(...) a rhizome or multiplicity never allows itself to be overcoded, never has available a supplementary dimension over and above its number of lines. (...) All multiplicities are flat, in the sense that they fill or occupy all of their dimensions. (...) Multiplicities are defined by the outside,; by the abstract line, the line of flight or deterritorialization according to which they change in nature and connect with other multiplicities.(...) The line of flight marks: (...) the impossibility of a supplementary dimension, unless the multiplicity is transformed by the line of flight; the possibility and necessity of flattening all of the multiplicities on a single plane of consistency or exteriority, regardless of their number of dimensions.(...) The rhizome [or multiplicity] is (...) a map and not a tracing. (...) What distinguishes the map from the tracing id that it is entirely oriented toward an experimentation in contact with the real. (...) It is a regrettable characteristic of the Western mind to relate expressions and actions to exterior or transcendent ends, instead of evaluating them on a plane of consistency on the basis of their intrinsic value." Cf. Deleuze and Guattari, op. cit., especially "Principle of multiplicity", pp 9-12-20-22.

Sector three

TO KEEP THEM COMPANY

Company for "Sector one":

-Richard Long-

Walking a line through leaves along an eight day mountain walk in Sobaeksan, Korea, 1993.

-Michael Heizer-

Circular Surface Planar Displacement Etching, New York City, 1972.

19 Circular Surface Planar Displacement Etching, 1972, etched in basalt block in sidewalk, New York City. Collection: Sam Wagstaff, New York.

-Paul Auster-

Quinn's maps of Stillman's walks. City of Glass, New York City, 1985.

Company for "Sector two. Level":

-Jorn Utzon-

Montealban, Platforms and Plateaus, Mexico 1949-1962.

- Michael Heizer-

Double Negative, 240,000 Ton displacement, Virgin River Mesa, 1969-1970.

-Gordon Matta-Clark-

Descending Steps for Batan, Galerie Yvon Lambert, Paris, 1977.

-Gordon Matta-Clark- (with Charles Simmonds and the kid Kyle Beuchat)
Fireboy, Brooklyn Bridge. New York City, 1971.

-Yves Brunier-(with Jean Nouvel)
Autoroutes du Sud de la France, Toll plaza at Vienne, 1988.

re-make/re-model

The present series of captioned images is set up from the observation of three apparently unrelated topics participating from the same horizon:

- Leveling the land.
- Consistency.
- Flatness as collapsed depth.

Re-make/re-model simply re-stages the paper as “Through the Looking-glass” is re-staged in the chess game at its opening.

Captions:

David Leatherbarrow: “Leveling the Land”, in “Recovering Landscape”, James Corner, editor. Princeton Architectural Press, 1999.

Peter Smithson: “Without Rhetoric”, Latimer New Dimensions, London, 1973.

Jorn Utzon: “Platforms and Plateaus: Ideas of a Danish Architect”, in “Zodiac”, 1962.

Vincent Scully: “The Earth, the Temple, and the Gods. Greek Sacred Architecture”, Yale University, 1962.

Jean-Claude Margueron: “Los Mesopotamicos”, Ediciones Catedra, Barcelona 1996.

Denis Cosgrove: “Liminal Geometry and Elemental Landscape”, in “Recovering Landscape”, James Corner, editor. Princeton Architectural Press, 1999.

Pherecydes of Syros: as quoted in Leatherbarrow, op. cit..

Michel De Certeau: “Walking the City”, in “The Practice of Everyday Life”, University of California Press, 1985.

Lewis Carroll: “Through the Looking-glass and what Alice found there”, in “The Annotated Alice”, Martin Gardiner, notes and introduction. Clarkson N. Potter, Inc./Publisher, New York, 1960.

Jorge Luis Borges: “La Muerte y la Brujula”, in “Obras Completas”, Emece Editores, Barcelona, 1994.

Gilbert Keith Chesterton: “The Club of Queer Trades”, Penguin, London.

Paul Auster: “City of Glass. The New York Trilogy , volume I”, Sun & Moon Press, Los Angeles, 1985.

Ptolemy: as quoted in Cosgrove, op. cit..

Sophie Calle: “Marriage” and “Suite Venetienne” in “Relatos”, Fundacio La Caixa, Barcelona, 1995. “Suite Venetienne” also published individually together with “Gotham’s Handbook” (Calle et Auster).

1-Leveling the land as the first and most fundamental act of topographical construction (*David Leatherbarrow*).

2-Platform as a primary topic in the sort of site construction that envisages inhabitation (*David Leatherbarrow*).

3-Rectangularity of platform as the essence of the Doric (*Peter Smithson*).

61 Podium and temple of Argive Heraeum: Charles Waldstein: Cambridge Press, 1902.

4-Elevated platforms to obtain a new dimension of life (*Jorn Utzon*).

5-It is therefore with the holiness of the earth that we must first be concerned
(*Vincent Scully*).

6-Dryness of the leveled land, the terrace (*David Leatherbarrow*).

7-Levelled land is not flat (*David Leatherbarrow*).

8-Pregnancy, *omphalos*, slight outward/upward bulge (*David Leatherbarrow*).

9-Discovering of the horizon as a pregnant profile (Jorn Utzon).

10-Leveled land, constructed ground.

11-Wounding the E-earth.

12-Terrace, site for inhabitation, as scab: dry wound.

13-Michael Heizer, double negative.

14-Ritual foundation of cities : inhabitation as fundamental violence (*Jean-Claude Margueron*).

15-Exterior film of the earth: flatness as collapsed depth.

16-The outer membrane of the earth defines (confines, reveals) the wet mass of unknowable earth (*David Leatherbarrow*).

17-Crust constructed by leveled land, as site for visibility.

18-It was only through edges that things were defined (*David Leatherbarrow*).

19-Earth crust-scab as inscribeable ground.

The Maze near St. Anne's Chapel, Sneinton, Nottinghamshire, from a drawing by Mrs. Robert Miles.

20-The shipwreck of Aristippus: spying geometrical shapes in the sand: “put you fears aside, for here are signs of men” (*Denis Cosgrove*).

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Frontispiece of David Gregory's edition of Euclid's *Opera* (Oxford, 1703)
illustrating the shipwreck of Aristippus as related by Vitruvius
in the Preface to Book VI of his *De architectura*.

21-Geometrically derived boundaries inscribed elemental surface patterns across the earth (*Denis Cosgrove*).

22-Zeus's marital veil for Chthonia, *parthenos* (*Pherecydes of Syros*).

23-To inscribe figures on the ground.

24-Writing on the ground through action. Action as writing on the ground (*Michel De Certeau*).

25-Richard Long's walks.

WALKING A LINE THROUGH LEAVES. ALONG AN EIGHT DAY MOUNTAIN WALK IN SOBBAEK SAN KOREA 1993

26-Alice uncovers the world as a chessboard (*Lewis Carroll*).

27-White pawn (Alice) to play, and win in eleven moves (*Lewis Carroll*).

Through the Looking-Glass

RED

WHITE

White Pawn (Alice) to play, and win in eleven moves.

- | | |
|---|--|
| 1. ALICE MEETS R. Q. | 1. R. Q. TO K. R'S 4TH |
| 2. ALICE THROUGH Q'S
3D (<i>by railway</i>)
TO Q'S 4TH (<i>Tweedle-
dum and Tweedledee</i>) | 2. W. Q. TO Q. B'S 4TH
(<i>after shawl</i>) |
| 3. ALICE MEETS W. Q.
(<i>with shawl</i>) | 3. W. Q. TO Q. B'S 5TH
(<i>becomes sheep</i>) |
| 4. ALICE TO Q'S 5TH
(<i>shop, river, shop</i>) | 4. W. Q. TO K. B'S 8TH
(<i>leaves egg on shelf</i>) |
| 5. ALICE TO Q'S 6TH
(<i>Humpty Dumpty</i>) | 5. W. Q. TO Q. B'S 8TH
(<i>flying from R. Kt.</i>) |
| 6. ALICE TO Q'S 7TH
(<i>forest</i>) | 6. R. KT. TO K'S 2ND (CH.) |
| 7. W. KT. TAKES R. KT. | 7. W. KT. TO K. B'S 5TH |
| 8. ALICE TO Q'S 8TH
(<i>coronation</i>) | 8. R. Q. TO K'S SQ.
(<i>examination</i>) |
| 9. ALICE BECOMES QUEEN | 9. QUEENS CASTLE |
| 10. ALICE CASTLES
(<i>feast</i>) | 10. W. Q. TO Q. R'S 6TH
(<i>soup</i>) |
| 11. ALICE TAKES R. Q.
AND WINS | |

28-Borges and writing on the city: the Death and the Compass (Jorge Luis Borges).

29-Major Brown and the Club of Queer Trades, retroactive Borges (*Gilbert Keith Chesterton*).

30-Quinn tracks Stillman: The Tower of Babel (*Paul Auster*).

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Then, looking carefully through his notes, he began to trace with his pen the movements Stillman had made on a single day—the first day he had kept a full record of the old man's wanderings. The result was as follows:

Quinn was struck by the way Stillman had skirted around the edge of the territory, not once venturing into the center. The diagram looked a little like a map of some imaginary state in the Midwest. Except for the eleven blocks up Broadway at the start, and the series of curlicues that represented Stillman's meanderings in Riverside Park, the picture also resembled a rectangle. On the other hand, given the quadrant structure of New York streets, it might also have been a zero or the letter "O".

Quinn went on to the next day and decided to see what would happen. The results were not at all the same.

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This picture made Quinn think of a bird, a bird of prey perhaps, with its wings spread, hovering aloft in the air. A moment later, this reading seemed far-fetched to him. The bird vanished, and in its stead there were only two abstract shapes, linked by the tiny bridge Stillman had formed by walking west on 83rd Street. Quinn paused for a moment to ponder what he was doing. Was he scribbling nonsense? Was he feeble-mindedly frittering away the evening, or was he trying to find something? Either response, he realized, was unacceptable. If he was simply killing time, why had he chosen such a painstaking way to do it? Was he so muddled that he no longer had the courage to think? On the other hand, if he was not merely diverting himself, what was he actually up to? It seemed to him that he was looking for a sign. He was ransacking the chaos of

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Stillman's movements for some glimmer of cogency. This implied only one thing: that he continued to disbelieve the arbitrariness of Stillman's actions. He wanted there to be a sense to them, no matter how obscure. This, in itself, was unacceptable. For it meant that Quinn was allowing himself to deny the facts, and this, as he well knew, was the worst thing a detective could do.

Nevertheless, he decided to go on with it. It was not late, not even eleven o'clock yet, and the truth was that it could do no harm. The results of the third map bore no resemblance to the other two.

There no longer seemed to be a question about what was happening. If he discounted the squiggles from the park, Quinn felt certain that he was looking at the letter "E". Assuming the first diagram had in fact represented the letter "O," then it seemed legitimate to assume that

31-The mathematical acts of surveying and leveling (*Ptolemy*).

32-Sophie Calle, *Suite Venetienne* and *The Husband* (Sophie Calle)

33-Zeus's marital veil for Chthonia, *parthenos* (*Pherecydes of Syros*).

34-Crafted character of Chthonia's *anacalypteria* (David Leatherbarrow).

35-On it he wove the [lines or divisions of the] earth, the ocean and the houses of the ocean (*Pherecydes of Syros*).

36-Landscape is a web of boundaries (*Joseph Brinckenhoff Jackson*).

37-Veil as map (*David Leatherbarrow*).

38-By means of the boundaries (veil) the earth was shown to be a livable horizon
(*David Leatherbarrow*).

39-Matter abbreviated into a mat (*David Leatherbarrow*).

40-The well as wound. Undermining of the mat's crust. (Varro).

Detalles de *Time Well*, 1971

41-Architecture as grounding.

Annex 1: Nine Flatbeds papers

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15862147>

Annex 2: *Provisional hints for a contemporary criticality: Tafuri vs Koolhaas*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15862006>